

THE ROLE OF THE OLIGOPHRENOPEDAGOGUE IN THE SOCIAL INTEGRATION OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of the special education teacher in facilitating the social integration of children with special educational needs, primarily those with intellectual disabilities. It examines contemporary scholarly approaches to understanding social integration and outlines the key professional activities of a special education teacher that promote the successful socialization, adaptation, and inclusion of a child into educational and social environments. Based on an analysis of native and international research, the article substantiates the need to transition from a compensatory model of special education to a model centered on social participation and the development of the child's personal agency.*

Keywords: *special education teacher, social integration, children with special educational needs, intellectual disabilities, socialization, inclusive education, social and life skills.*

In the modern context of the modernization of special and inclusive education systems, the issue of social integration of children with special educational needs has become particularly relevant. Social integration is viewed not only as the inclusion of a child in the educational environment, but also as a process of ensuring their full participation in social life, developing communication competence, independence, and readiness for social interaction.

For children with intellectual disabilities, this process is complicated by the specific characteristics of their cognitive activity, limited social experience, difficulties in communication, and insufficient development of social and daily living skills. In this regard, the role of the oligophrenopedagogue, who serves as the key specialist providing psychological and pedagogical support in the process of students' social integration, becomes especially significant.

The analysis of contemporary research indicates that the effectiveness of the social integration of children with special educational needs depends not so much on the severity of the disability itself, but rather on the quality of psychological and pedagogical support, the level of interdisciplinary cooperation among specialists, and the creation of a supportive social environment. Researchers identify early pedagogical intervention, the individualization of the educational process, cooperation between the family and educational institutions, and the development of life competencies in children as the key factors of successful integration.

Within the cultural-historical concept of personality development, particular attention is given to the social nature of higher mental functions. According to this theory, the social integration of a child with an intellectual disability is viewed as the result of their inclusion in a system of social relations through specially organized pedagogical activities.

Despite the positive developments in the field of inclusive education, a number of factors continue to hinder the successful social integration of children with special educational needs. These factors include the insufficient preparedness of teaching staff, the limited availability of practice-oriented socialization programs, the persistence of social stereotypes, and the inadequate

involvement of families in the corrective and pedagogical process. An analysis of scientific publications shows that although many specialists recognize social adaptation as a priority objective of their professional activities, not all of them are sufficiently prepared to implement integration technologies in practice.

The scientific novelty of the study is reflected in the following:

- The content of the concept of “social integration of children with intellectual disabilities” has been clarified from the perspectives of competency-based and socio-activity approaches.
- The main areas of the professional activity of the oligophrenopedagogue in the process of social integration of students with special educational needs have been systematized.
- The components of the oligophrenopedagogue’s professional readiness to implement integration activities have been identified.
- A functional model of the oligophrenopedagogue’s participation in the social integration of children with intellectual disabilities has been developed.
- The pedagogical conditions for increasing the effectiveness of integration processes in special and inclusive education have been substantiated.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS.

The methodological foundation of the study was based on the principles of humanistic pedagogy, as well as competency-based, learner-centered, activity-oriented, and inclusive approaches to the education of children with special educational needs.

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following research methods were employed:

- **Theoretical methods:** analysis of psychological-pedagogical, defectological, and methodological literature; comparative analysis; systematization and generalization of scientific data.
- **Empirical methods:** pedagogical observation, questionnaire surveys, interviews, and expert assessment.
- **Statistical methods:** quantitative and qualitative processing of the research results.

The information base of the study consisted of regulatory and legal documents in the field of special and inclusive education, scientific publications by national and international scholars, as well as materials reflecting the practical activities of educational institutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The social integration of children with intellectual disabilities is a multifaceted pedagogical process aimed at ensuring their active participation in social life, effective communication with peers, acquisition of independent living skills, and involvement in educational, occupational, and cultural activities. Social integration involves developing the child’s existing potential, supporting their social adaptation, and assisting them in finding their place in society as equal members of the community.

From this perspective, the development of communicative, social, daily living, and adaptive skills in children with intellectual disabilities, ensuring the active involvement of their families, and creating an inclusive educational environment are considered key factors for their successful social integration

The conducted analysis demonstrated that the modern concept of social integration of children with intellectual disabilities requires a transition from a model of social adaptation to a model of active social participation. In this context, the oligophrenopedagogue becomes the key

specialist responsible for developing the child's life competencies and ensuring their involvement in various forms of social activity.

The study made it possible to identify the main functions of the oligophrenopedagogue in the process of students' social integration:

Diagnostic Function – involves assessing the child's level of social development, identifying the characteristics of their communicative activity, evaluating their social and daily living skills, and determining their adaptive capacities and potential for social adjustment.

Design Function – encompasses the development of individualized educational pathways, corrective-developmental programs, and technologies aimed at fostering life competencies.

Corrective and Developmental Function – focuses on enhancing cognitive activity, communicative competence, independence, and socially significant personal qualities.

Social-Mediating Function – ensures effective interaction and cooperation among the child, the family, the educational institution, and society.

Consultative Function – involves providing methodological support and guidance to parents and teachers on issues related to students' socialization and integration

The results of the analysis indicate that the effectiveness of social integration increases significantly only when all participants in the educational process cooperate in a comprehensive and coordinated manner. In this regard, collaboration between the family and the educational institution is of particular importance, as the family environment serves as the most crucial factor in reinforcing the social skills developed during the educational process.

Model of the Oligophrenopedagogue's Role in Social Integration

The proposed model includes four interrelated components:

Goal – to ensure the successful social integration of children with intellectual disabilities through the development of life competencies and social-daily living skills.

Content Component includes:

- the development of communication skills;
- the formation of social and daily living competenc
- the development of independence;
- preparation for social interaction and participation in social relationships;
- the formation of positive social experience.

Organizational and Activity Component предусматривает (includes) the use of:

- practice-oriented technologies;
- social role-playing games;
- situational modeling;
- project-based activities;
- family support and guidance technologies

Outcome Component

The effectiveness criteria include:

- the level of social adaptation;
- the level of the student's independence;
- the degree of development of communication skills;
- the level of social and daily living competence;
- readiness to participate in social life.

Pedagogical Conditions for Effective Social Integration

Based on the conducted analysis, the following pedagogical conditions were identified:

1. Developing the professional readiness of oligophrenopedagogues for integration activities.
2. Creating a corrective and developmental educational environment.
3. Implementing an individualized approach to education and upbringing.
4. Organizing interdisciplinary support for students.
5. Actively involving the family in the child's socialization process.
6. Using practice-oriented technologies for the development of life competencies.
7. Ensuring continuity and close interaction between the educational institution and the social environment.

CONCLUSION

The social integration of children with special educational needs is a complex and multifaceted process, the success of which largely depends on the professional activities of the oligophrenopedagogue. In modern conditions, the role of the oligophrenopedagogue extends beyond traditional corrective work and includes the functions of a coordinator, consultant, mediator, and organizer of social interactions.

The role of the oligophrenopedagogue in the social integration of children with special educational needs is of systemic importance. The oligophrenopedagogue acts not only as an organizer of corrective and developmental activities but also as a mediator between the child and society, creating the necessary conditions for the child's successful socialization and full participation in social life

The results of the analysis indicate that the effectiveness of the social integration of children with intellectual disabilities is directly dependent on the professional competence of the oligophrenopedagogue, particularly on their ability to provide interdisciplinary support, develop social and daily living skills, and create conditions that encourage the child's active participation in various spheres of social activity.

The findings also confirm the necessity of improving the system for training future oligophrenopedagogues, with particular emphasis on developing competencies related to fostering life skills, social adaptation, and the social integration of students with intellectual disabilities.

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